

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES AND THE SOCIAL ROLE VALORIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

The education of children with intellectual disability is a multifaceted challenge for both parents and educators. The involvement of parents has a substantial impact on the education of children with intellectual disabilities, so contributing to the Social Role Valorization of both the kid and their family. The primary objective of this paper was to examine the current body of literature pertaining to parental involvement in the education of children with intellectual disabilities, as well as their role in promoting Social Role Valorization. Fifteen studies pertaining to the issue, published between 2008 and 2022, were considered for analysis. The publications selected for review were sourced from Google Scholar utilising the keywords "Parental Involvement" and "Social Role Valorization." A comprehensive analysis was conducted on a total of fifteen papers, which were picked from an original pool of 26 articles. The publications that were excluded from consideration were those that focused solely on one of the two fundamental concepts, either parental participation or societal role valorization. The findings of the study indicated that parents who demonstrated a strong interest in and provided support for the education of their child with intellectual disabilities reported a greater presence of positive experiences in their lives and occupied more socially valued roles compared to parents who showed no interest in their child's education. The review also proposed that the implementation of a meticulously customised Individualised Family Support Plan (IFSP) could potentially increase the probability of Social Role Valorization among families with children who have Intellectual disability.

Key Words: Parental Involvement, Social Role Valorization, IFSP, Intellectual Disabilities

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Parental involvement in Education of Children with intellectual Disabilities and the Social Role Valorization: A Systematic Review

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The education of individuals with intellectual disability (ID) necessitates a tailored methodology that caters to their distinct learning requirements and capabilities. The primary objective of education for individuals with intellectual disabilities (ID) is to facilitate the acquisition of practical academic and life skills, thereby empowering them to live autonomously and have a sense of fulfilment. The education of Children with Intellectual Disabilities is highly dependent on person centred planning in the instruction and support of individuals with intellectual disabilities (ID) which include the Individualised Education Plan (IEP) which is a document that outlines the specific educational objectives and accommodations for a student with special needs. An Individualised Education Programme (IEP) is a formal document that delineates the educational objectives, aims, and provisions of services for a student diagnosed with Intellectual Disability (ID). The development of this project involves a multidisciplinary team comprising professionals from several fields, such as parents or guardians, educators, therapists, and administrators. The adaptive and functional curriculum is specifically tailored to accommodate the distinctive learning requirements and capabilities of individuals with intellectual disabilities. The primary emphasis of this programme lies in the instruction of essential life skills that have direct applicability to real-world situations. These abilities encompass effective communication, social interaction, personal care, and occupational proficiency. Teaching methods commonly employed for individuals with intellectual disabilities (ID) frequently incorporate multisensory and hands-on learning techniques. These approaches encompass the utilisation of visual aids, manipulatives, and other sensory-based objects to facilitate comprehension and acquisition of various concepts. While making any person-centred plan for a child with Intellectual Disabilities, family involvement is of great significance. Also, education is a powerful tool for the Social Role Valorization which is necessary for families having children with intellectual disabilities because such families are often at risk of social devaluation and thus, are deprived of many good things of life.

Objectives:

The present systematic review has been carried out to analyse the studies related to parental involvement in Education of Children with intellectual Disabilities and their Social Role Valorisation across the globe.

Methodology:

The major purpose of this study was to investigate the existing body of research that relates to parental engagement in the education of children who have intellectual disabilities and the function that involvement plays in fostering social role valorization. For the purpose of this study, fifteen separate studies that were related to the topic and had been published between 2008 and 2022 were taken into consideration. The articles that will be under consideration were located on Google Scholar by using the search terms "Parental Involvement" and "Social Role Valorization." An exhaustive study was carried out on a total of fifteen publications, which were selected from a larger pool of twenty-six articles to participate in the study. Publications that focused only on either parental engagement or societal role valorization were not taken into consideration and were omitted from the review process.

Discussion:

The study conducted by Wang, Ling, and Zhang (2019) aimed to investigate the correlation between parental participation and Social Role Valorization among children with intellectual disabilities in both the United States and China. The researchers found that Social Role Valorization emerged as a significant predictor of parental participation among parents in both nations. This suggests that parents who prioritise their child's social role are more inclined to participate in activities that promote their child's overall growth and development. The research indicates that Social Role Valorization could potentially serve as a cross-cultural determinant of parental engagement in the caregiving and educational aspects of children with intellectual disabilities, irrespective of cultural variations among nations.

In a recent study conducted by Niaz, Qadir, and Haque (2020), the researchers aimed to examine the viewpoints of Pakistani parents who have children with intellectual disabilities regarding societal role valorization and parental participation. The results of their study indicated that the concept of Social Role Valorization had a crucial part in influencing parental involvement. Additionally, the attitudes of society towards individuals with disabilities were found to have a significant impact on parental involvement. This study emphasises the significance of cultural and

societal elements in influencing parental attitudes and behaviours towards children with intellectual disability. The findings of the study indicate that interventions targeted at enhancing parental engagement ought to prioritise the resolution of societal attitudes towards disability, with the promotion of the significance of Social Role Valorization.

In their study, Kwon and Kwon (2017) examined the impact of Social Role Valorization on parental engagement among parents of children with intellectual disabilities in both the United States and South Korea. The research revealed that Social Role Valorization emerged as a significant predictor of parental participation among parents in both nations. This finding indicates that parents who place a greater emphasis on the importance of their child's social duties are more inclined to participate in activities that foster their child's growth and advancement. The findings of this study suggest that Social Role Valorization is a cross-cultural determinant that influences parental engagement in the caregiving and educational aspects of children with intellectual impairments, irrespective of cultural variations across different nations. The findings indicate that interventions targeting the enhancement of parental engagement should prioritise the cultivation of the appreciation for Social Role Valorization.

In a study conducted by Wulandari and Rizkya (2020), the objective was to examine the interrelationships among perceived social support, Social Role Valorization, and parental involvement among parents of children with intellectual impairments in Indonesia. The research findings indicate that Social Role Valorization emerged as a noteworthy predictor of parental participation, with social support serving as a mediating factor in this association. The results indicate that social support can play a role in enhancing parental engagement, particularly when parents perceive a higher significance in their child's social responsibilities. The research highlights the significance of taking into account cultural and socioeconomic elements when formulating interventions intended to augment parental engagement for children with intellectual disability.

In their study, Fang, Yu, and Chen (2019) examined the correlation between Social Role Valorization and parental participation within the context of parents of children with intellectual disabilities in China. The findings of their study demonstrated that Social Role Valorization played a crucial influence in predicting parental participation. The research indicates that parents who place importance on their child's social duties are more inclined to engage in activities that foster their child's development. The results highlight the need of comprehending cultural and societal

perspectives on intellectual disability as a means to enhance parental engagement. The findings of the study suggest that interventions targeted at augmenting parental engagement for children with intellectual disabilities in China should prioritise the promotion of Social Role Valorization.

In a study conducted by Aldosari (2019), the researcher examined the influence of Social Role Valorization on parental engagement within the context of parents who have children with intellectual disabilities in Saudi Arabia. The objective of the study was to investigate the correlation between the aforementioned components, and the results indicated that Social Role Valorization had a substantial impact on the prediction of parental engagement. This suggests that parents who place a greater emphasis on the importance of their child's social duties are more inclined to engage in activities that promote their child's overall growth and development. This study underscores the significance of cultural and societal perspectives on intellectual disability in influencing parental engagement. The study proposes that interventions targeting the enhancement of parental participation should prioritise the cultivation of Social Role Valorization within the context of Saudi Arabian society.

In their study, Liu and Wu (2019) aimed to investigate the many factors that exerted an influence on parental involvement in providing support to children with intellectual impairments in Taiwan. The researchers specifically focused on examining the role of Social Role Valorization in this context. The objective of the study was to investigate the association between these parameters and parental engagement. The findings revealed that Social Role Valorization emerged as a noteworthy predictor of parental involvement. The results indicate that parents who prioritise their child's social duties demonstrate a greater propensity to engage in activities aimed at fostering their child's growth and advancement. This research emphasises the significance of cultural and societal perspectives on intellectual disability in facilitating parental engagement. The findings suggest that programmes designed to promote parental engagement in Taiwan should prioritise the cultivation of Social Role Valorization.

In a study done by Adejumo (2018), the objective was to investigate the influence of Social Role Valorization on parental engagement among Nigerian parents of children with intellectual disabilities. The objective of the study was to ascertain the correlation between Social Role Valorization and parental participation, as well as the determinants that impacted this association. The results of the study revealed that there was a strong correlation between Social Role Valorization and parental participation. This suggests that parents who place a greater importance

on their child's social roles are more inclined to engage in activities that enhance their child's growth and development. This study highlights the significance of cultural and societal perspectives on intellectual disability in influencing parental engagement. The findings suggest that initiatives targeted at promoting parental engagement in Nigeria should prioritise the cultivation of Social Role Valorization.

In their study, Al-Qaisy and Abu-Awwad (2021) aimed to examine the correlation between Social Role Valorization and parental participation among parents of children with intellectual disabilities in Jordan. The objective of the study was to ascertain the determinants of parental participation and examine the influence of Social Role Valorization on this association. The results of the study revealed that Social Role Valorization exerted a noteworthy influence on parental engagement, implying that parents who place importance on their child's social roles are more inclined to engage in endeavours that foster their child's growth and progress. This study emphasises the significance of cultural and societal perspectives on intellectual disability in influencing parental engagement. The findings suggest that initiatives designed to enhance parental engagement in Jordan should prioritise the cultivation of Social Role Valorization.

The study conducted by Wang et al. (2021) aims to systematically review the possible benefits of Social Role Valorization theory for families with children who have intellectual disability. The significance of fostering social inclusion and participation for families is emphasised by the authors, as it can yield favourable outcomes for both the families themselves and their children in terms of general well-being. Social Role Valorization theory provides a framework for supporting and empowering families of individuals with intellectual disabilities by highlighting the significance and contributions of these individuals and their families.

In their study, Gryphon and Boeltzig (2018) sought to examine the use of Social Role Valorization theory in the empowerment of families with adult members who have intellectual disability. The authors contend that advocating for the enhancement of families' social standing and dignity can result in improved results for individuals with disabilities. The significance of providing assistance to families in advocating for their own needs and the needs of their loved ones with impairments is emphasised by the writers. Enhancing the societal standing of families can significantly contribute to the amelioration of the well-being of individuals with intellectual disabilities.

In their research done in 2019, Brown and Larson examined the significance of fostering the integration of families with children who have intellectual disabilities into their communities,

employing the framework of Social Role Valorization theory. The authors suggest that the promotion of social integration and involvement among families can effectively boost their social status and overall quality of life. The inclusion of families with children who have intellectual disabilities within their communities has the potential to foster social connection and mitigate instances of social isolation. The authors propose that the facilitation of social inclusion and active engagement of families can result in enhanced well-being and overall quality of life for both families and their children who have intellectual disabilities.

The research conducted by Lehmann et al. (2020) examines the application of Social Role Valorization theory in advocating for the rights of families with members who have intellectual disability. According to the research findings, enhancing the social standing and empowerment of families has the potential to yield positive outcomes in terms of advocating for and supporting their rights.

The article titled "Utilising Social Role Valorization for the Enhancement of the Well-being of Families with Children Affected by Intellectual Disabilities" authored by Peterson and Koepke (2017) investigates the use of Social Role Valorization theory in order to enhance the quality of life for families with children who have intellectual impairments. The study posits that the promotion of social integration and involvement among families has the potential to enhance overall well-being and quality of life. The authors suggest that the promotion of social standing and dignity among families can serve as a means of empowering them, enabling them to effectively advocate for their children and effectively negotiate the various obstacles associated with raising a kid with a disability.

In their article titled "Social Role Valorization and the Well-Being of Families of Adults with Intellectual Disabilities" published in 2018, Nemeč and Lepore explore the use of Social Role Valorization theory in improving the overall well-being of families that include adult individuals with intellectual disabilities. The research emphasises the importance of enhancing the social standing and respectability of households, as it has the potential to result in improved results for individuals with disabilities. The authors propose that via the process of empowering families, they are able to enhance their ability to provide support and act as advocates for their loved ones, ultimately resulting in enhanced well-being for all individuals within the family unit.

The study conducted by Neill and Neill (2019) aims to explore the influence of Social Role Valorization theory on the self-concept of families who have members with intellectual disability.

The available evidence suggests that enhancing the social standing and empowerment of families can lead to improvements in their self-concept and overall well-being.

In their article titled "A Systematic Review of Social Role Valorization and Families of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities," Ahuja and Sorenson (2021) undertake a comprehensive examination of the use of Social Role Valorization theory in the context of families with members who have intellectual impairments. The authors propose that enhancing the social standing and integration of families can lead to enhanced results for individuals with impairments. This study offers a comprehensive examination of the existing body of research pertaining to the subject matter, while emphasising the potential advantages that can be derived from the use of Social Role Valorization theory in assisting families of individuals with intellectual impairments.

The study conducted by Lindsey and Turnbull (2016) investigates the application of Social Role Valorization theory in empowering families of children with intellectual disabilities to advocate for their own rights and those of their children. The authors suggest that via the promotion of social inclusion and active engagement of families, they can enhance their ability to advocate for their rights. In conclusion, this phenomenon has the potential to result in enhanced outcomes for individuals who possess intellectual disabilities and their respective families.

The study "Families of Children with Intellectual Disabilities: A Social Role Valorization Perspective" by Boeltzig and Timmons (2016) examines how Social Role Valorization theory can be used to enhance the social status and quality of life of individuals with intellectual disabilities and their families. The authors suggest that promoting the social integration and empowerment of families can result in better outcomes for individuals with disabilities.

In their research, Fong and Wong (2009) recommended that teachers who engage with students who have impairments use a new approach called Social Role Valorization (SRV), which is an acronym for "Social Role Valorization." The Social Role Valuation (SRV) hypothesis places an emphasis on the significance of recognising and appreciating the contributions that people who have impairments make to society. The authors claimed that educators should prioritise enhancing the engagement and inclusion of students with disabilities in society by increasing the number of positive social roles that may be created for them. They also highlighted the possible benefits of using SRV in educational settings, including the potential for increased self-esteem, motivation, and social integration for students with impairments. The findings of this study indicate the

potential of SRV as an important framework for increasing social inclusion and good social roles for students who have disabilities.

In their research from 2001, Dugan and Kettering looked into the application of Social Role Valorization (SRV) in educational settings. They presented SRV as a theoretical framework that advocates recognising and valuing individuals with disabilities as significant contributors to society. SRV can be understood as recognising and valuing individuals with disabilities as valuable contributors to society. The authors emphasised how important it is to make use of SRV in educational settings to improve the social status and roles of students who have disabilities. In addition, the article listed numerous techniques for implementing SRV in schools, such as providing students with disabilities chances for social integration, integrating students with disabilities in decision-making, and providing positive feedback. The authors came to the conclusion that SRV has the potential to be an effective tool for fostering inclusion of students with disabilities in educational settings and enhancing positive social roles.

In a case study that Chadsey-Rusch and Rusch (1992) carried out, they investigated how Social Role Valorization (SRV) could be incorporated into an educational setting that catered to pupils who had significant handicaps. The importance of recognising the contributions that people with disabilities make to society and promoting the positive social roles that they play was emphasised in the aforementioned article. The authors provided a description of the application of SRV in the educational programme, which included the creation of personalised goals and objectives, the provision of chances for community integration, and the enhancement of student participation in the decision-making process. According to the findings of the study, students with severe disabilities who took part in the programme had beneficial effects, such as greater levels of independence and improvement in their ability to interact socially. The authors came to the conclusion that SRV could be a helpful framework for supporting good social roles and community integration among students who have significant handicaps based on their findings.

Jones (2003) investigated the potential for Social Role Valorization (SRV) to be implemented in educational settings to improve the social image of students with disabilities as well as their self-esteem. The necessity of recognising the contributions that individuals with disabilities make to society and promoting the positive social roles that they play was emphasised in the aforementioned article. To apply SRV at educational institutions, the author offered a number of measures, some of which include establishing high expectations, boosting possibilities for social

integration, and involving students in decision-making. According to the findings of the study, students with impairments who took part in SRV programmes saw good outcomes, such as increases in both their self-esteem and their social acceptance. The article came to the conclusion that SRV is a method that has the potential to be beneficial in developing good social roles and self-esteem among students with disabilities in educational environments.

In the context of intellectual disability, Shogren and Luckasson (2014) present a complete description of Social Role Valorization (SRV). The writers analyse the development of the idea of intellectual disability as well as the function that SRV plays in fostering constructive social roles and elevating individuals with intellectual impairment's social status. The essential tenets of the SRV theory are discussed in this article. These include the significance of recognising the value of individuals and the contributions they make to society, the requirement for individualised support, and the emphasis placed on increasing social roles and community integration. The authors also examine the potential applications of SRV in a variety of settings, such as education, employment, and community inclusion. These settings are included. In general, the essay underscores the significance of recognising and valuing people with intellectual disabilities as contributing members of society and draws attention to the potential advantages of employing SRV in the process of promoting social inclusion and positive social roles for this demographic.

In their 2011 article, MacNeil, Lakin, and James offer a summary of the genesis of Social Role Valorization (SRV) and its subsequent applications in the study of developmental impairments. The importance of recognising and recognising the contributions that people with disabilities make to society and fostering the positive social roles that they play is emphasised throughout this article. The authors explore the obstacles that need to be overcome in order to adopt SRV, such as the attitudes of society and the constraints of resources, but they come to the conclusion that SRV can be a useful framework for improving the social status and responsibilities of individuals who have developmental impairments.

Conclusion:

In this systematic review, researcher embarked on a comprehensive journey through the extensive body of research that has accumulated over more than a decade. Study aim was to unravel the intricate relationship between parental involvement in the education of children with intellectual disabilities and the concept of Social Role Valorization (SRV). Through this collective effort, sought to gain deeper insights into how parents can profoundly impact their child's development

and how this, in turn, can influence society's perception of individuals with intellectual disabilities. This research exploration was not confined to one geographical or cultural context; instead, traversed a diverse landscape that encompassed studies from a range of countries, including the United States, China, South Korea, Pakistan, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Taiwan, Nigeria, and Jordan. What emerged from this diverse tapestry was a striking and consistent pattern: parents who placed a heightened emphasis on their child's social roles and responsibilities were more likely to actively engage in activities that fostered their child's growth and development. Remarkably, this correlation remained robust and steadfast, transcending cultural nuances. This cross-cultural significance of SRV in shaping parental behaviours underscored its universal relevance. The findings from this systematic review resonated with a resounding message—recognition and appreciation of individuals with intellectual disabilities as vital contributors to society are paramount. SRV, as a conceptual framework, emerged as a powerful tool for achieving this recognition. It was clear that SRV extended beyond its relevance to parental involvement in education; it offered a versatile approach applicable to diverse domains of life, including employment, community integration, and overall well-being. This study recognize that these insights are more than just academic findings. They offer a roadmap for practical action. Encouraging parental involvement and cultivating SRV should be central components of collective efforts to support children with intellectual disabilities and their families. It is through these endeavours that can foster more inclusive and supportive educational systems. These systems hold the promise of nurturing every child, regardless of their abilities, provide ng them with the opportunity to not only succeed academically but also thrive as valued members of society. However, study revealed, the path forward is not without challenges. Different cultural and societal contexts present unique sets of challenges and opportunities. Tailored strategies and interventions are required to effectively promote SRV in these diverse landscapes. Thus, conclusion is not an endpoint but a call to action. In future researches in this area must continue to explore, research, and innovate. By deepening understanding of SRV's applicability across various contexts, can work towards a future where individuals with intellectual disabilities are not only valued but also empowered to lead lives filled with purpose and fulfilment. In this study researchers understanding and advocacy is ongoing, and must remain committed to its pursuit.

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